

////////////////////////////////////
THE VISUAL CODING OF (BIG) QUALITATIVE DATA:
NEW ANALYTIC METHODS AND TOOLS FOR EMERGING ONLINE RESEARCH

Kim Erwin, Assistant Professor
IIT Institute of Design, Chicago, IL USA
kerwin@id.iit.edu

ABSTRACT

Emerging online research platforms are bringing new efficiencies to the design research process. But the resulting data is large in scope and dense in nature. And the analytic tools and approaches design teams have come to rely on were not designed to manage this scale of inquiry. As design problems expand in complexity and require more inputs, generating big qualitative data sets is likely to become the new norm. This paper proposes two ways to manage this new condition: (1) adding visual coding techniques to textual coding to counteract "data sameness" and "data sprawl," and (2) developing new tools to support fast meta explorations of data sets.

Keywords: analytic methods, analytic tools, data visualization, design research

INTRODUCTION

Emerging online research platforms—a class of data collection tools that rely on user self-reporting via technology-mediated researcher/participant interactions—appear on the surface to offer design teams the opportunity to gather large amounts of rich, first-person data with attractive efficiencies in timing and reach.

However, as online platforms bring unparalleled access to new users—in particular hard-to-access and globally-dispersed participants—and capture rich media inputs, design teams are witnessing a geometric pileup of data that is large in scope and dense in nature. This is increasingly a modern condition of practice: design problems are expanding in complexity and so require more inputs. The resulting generation of big qualitative data sets is likely a new norm.

Online research platforms are also changing the nature of user research data. Because these tools rely on self-reporting, the research activities tend to be focused or discrete—a diary entry for instance rather than a long-form interview. These activities tend to yield data “snippets,” a small and optimal unit of information for both users and researchers.

The “snippet” size is useful for study participants because it fits their busy lifestyles and makes compliance easy to achieve. It’s equally useful for researchers because this unit of information—an image with an explanation or story, or a two-minute video clip—offers clean, bounded data moments that are easy to digest, tag, interpret and synthesize.

Today’s online research platforms have reasonable display systems for individual participant answers, but have almost no analytic tools to handle comparisons, clustering and coding. The analytic tools and approaches design teams have come to rely on are not designed to manage this volume of data. Analysis of large qualitative data sets, therefore, requires export to flexible, accessible analytic tools like Excel, where data loses important visual context, resulting in what might be called “data sameness.” At the same time, the data also expands beyond the navigable visual field of the analyst, generating “data sprawl” (see figure 1) This new condition challenges time-honored bottom-up analytic processes and tools, and more than reclaims the efficiencies gained in the online data collection process.

This paper proposes two approaches to managing the data sprawl and data sameness generated by online qualitative research. Approach 1 looks at simple visual coding strategies to reduce the visual plane of the data and create a more compact, visually differentiated analytic environment. This leverages

Figure 1. Data sprawl and data sameness are evident in this snapshot of otherwise rich user data. Here we see the output of an online diary—a diary of 25 women tracking all internet usage for 10 days that generated 236 entries embedded in 1888 cells—displayed in Excel. Extended text can overload the analyst, producing fatigue and cognitive workarounds that skew interpretation and limit insight.

the human capacity for pre-cognitive processing of data, or what data visualization specialist Stephen Few (2009) calls *thinking with our eyes*. Approach 2 looks to define a new class of analytic tools that can permit “data poking”—fast, simple and visual meta explorations of data that can suggest and frame more robust analytic strategies at the ground level. In particular, this paper showcases one such new tool: a prototype “app” that processes raw data into an interactive display of itself. This visualization tool, by keeping the raw data just below the surface, preserves the critical context of that data for quick investigation by the design team, offering seamless transition between macro (pattern level) views and micro (detail and instance level) views.

1 VISUAL CODING STRATEGIES

The application of basic principles of visual perception, cognition, pattern detection and sense-

making capabilities of humans to the visualization of large data sets has been in development in quantitative analysis for decades. Tools like Tableau and SPSS embody many of the core principles developed by quantitative researchers. The question posed in this paper is how might the design research community adapt data visualization techniques developed in the *quantitative* context for better management of complex user data in the *qualitative* context?

As author and data visualization expert Stephen Few (2009) notes, humans are extraordinarily good at “thinking with our eyes,” taking in simultaneously the holistic image of a visually-represented data set, as well as perceiving the individual properties (length, width, area, shape, color, orientation and location) that compose it. Using Excel, a visually-skilled analyst can apply several useful design

Figure 3. In this variation of Figure 2, entries are color-coded to reflect the life stage of the participant. Color and position create “families” or visual clusters, of entries on the left, while on the right only color is used, limiting the eye’s ability to differentiate clusters. In both cases, without having read a single entry, the analyst can quickly see that the orange group—40-something women with kids—have created a disproportionate number of the entries. Again every cell contains the raw data and can be viewed in the formula bar, allowing for quick exploration of instances and clusters.

REMEDYING DATA SAMENESS

This new, compact presentation resembles a bar chart—a quantitative convention. But counting is not the desired (or relevant) outcome with qualitative. What is desirable with qualitative is to make distinctions and to highlight patterns of similarity. For this, we can turn to Jacques Bertin’s (1967,1984) six retinal variables—size, value, color, pattern, orientation and shape—to visually code established variables in the data so that surface patterns or problems can be observed, just as they might in a quantitative visualization.

In Figure 3, the simple application of color to each entry—visually coding the life stage of the study participant by color—effectively creates a map of the entries that allows for pre-cognitive perception. That is, without having to read each individual entry, we can visually identify what Bertin (1984) would call a “selective relationship” between entries made by participants of the same study segment because of color and position. A selective relationship allows “marks to be perceived as different [from others],

forming families.” The presenting family or pattern in Figure 3 can’t be missed: an overwhelming number of entries are orange. Clearly one segment of the study generated a disproportionate number of entries. Without having read a single entry, the analyst has surfaced an interesting issue to investigate.

One of the features of this approach—visually coding data so that it might form an interface to itself—is that the data can be read at both a micro and a macro level *simultaneously*. At the macro level, the analyst can see a holistic picture and any patterns revealed by the coding choices. At the micro level, the analyst can dwell on the individual instances that comprise the data or browse a particular cluster without losing connection to the whole.

This ability to explore data *in context* and *in a single, unified browsing environment*—is critical to the sense-making process. And current qualitative tools do not provide this kind of exploratory environment.

Figure 4. This represents 118 total shopping log entries of study participants as a series of bars. Shopping entries are distributed by shopping channel on the horizontal axis (browsed offline/purchased online, etc.). And then segmented into two groups: shopped for self or shopped for others, exploring the analyst's hypothesis that shopping behavior may differ depending on whom the purchases are for. Bright green bars draw attention to purchases that fall within the retail client's offerings, allowing them to track categories of interest. In this case, the analyst chose to embody the raw user data using Excel's comment function, indicated by the red triangles. Analysis and design by Elizabeth Taggart, MDes 2011

This approach is particularly useful for helping researchers see *categorical variables*—those that can be expressed only in words—which quantitative experts distinguish from *quantitative variables* that can be expressed in numbers.

VARIATIONS IN VISUAL CODING

Coding categorical variables is useful and the obvious candidate for tool support, but other analytic processes can benefit from visual treatment. Two are explored here: visual coding based on hypothesis and visual coding based on inference.

Figure 4 is an example of organizing and visually coding data based on a hypothesis. The analyst organizes the output of a shopping log kept by study participants, segmenting data horizontally by various browsing/purchasing channels, and vertically by the hypothesis that shopping for self versus shopping for others may yield different priorities or behaviors. This reveals that most shopping by study participants

in their 30s and 40s with children was largely for others and carried out fairly evenly between online and offline environments (groceries being the notable exception, represented in the long brown bar in the top graph). Participants in their 40s also appeared to made more overall purchases for themselves than participants in their 30s.

This approach is interesting because it represents a hybrid strategy of organizing data by one predefined variable that is built into the data collection process (therefore well-defined and “clean”) and one variable that is inferred after the data has been collected. As such, it is one step removed from the first set of representations that code only predefined variables. This offers a second category of visual inquiry that fits the design research process in particular: Design researchers must often form hypotheses after a cursory review of data, especially when their job is to spark the design process. This second approach gives the design team a means of

Figure 5. This represents the same 118 shopping log entries offered in figure 4, but uses line weight and line color to capture the analyst’s interpretation of the shopping entries as to whether they were “want to buy” versus “need to buy” purchases. Each shopping entry is again represented by a square, with the raw data and voice of the study participant embedded in the square and viewable in the formula bar. The underlying chart form represents predefined variables sought in the data collection process, but the layering of visually-coded interpretation captures an interplay between fact and inference that is all-too-often invisible in design thinking. Analysis and design by Owen Shoppe, MDes 2011

testing hypotheses early and quickly to see if they hold water, and to see if they are likely to add value to the project.

Figure 5 is an example of organizing and visually coding data based on an inference. An inference is two steps removed from the coding of predefined variables in the first set of examples. Here, the analyst uses a base layer of predefined variables, using color and horizontal and vertical position to represent two of these variables (category shopped and channel shopped). On top of this, the analyst adds line weight and line color to reflect the analyst’s interpretation of each entry. In this instance, the analyst was interested in whether the purchase was a “needed to buy” or a “wanted to buy” moment, and sought to compare this split in motivation to the channel shopped.

This approach represents a third approach to visual inquiry that has subtle but important contributions to make to the analysis process: it makes explicit the

interplay between fact and inference that is all-too-often hard to discern (because it’s embodied in text) and in practical terms is accessible only to the analyst who wrote it. Here, team members can quickly identify the inferences and resulting patterns, poke at the logic and credibility of those inferences, engage in dialogue regarding the usefulness and credibility of the emerging process and findings, and move toward consensus. By exposing the logic visually, teams can immerse themselves without protracted reading, and either proceed with confidence or course-correct early on.

This idea of coding inferences is perhaps the biggest departure from quantitative practice, but also holds great potential for qualitative analysis. Design researchers often have instincts about data that can be easily visually coded—responses that stand out, or appear more or less useful, odd or representative, stronger or weaker. Using visual coding to mark them, these instincts can be quickly tracked and collected or discarded as the analysis progresses. By

making the researcher's thinking visual, we make it visible and "findable" in a sea of data. This should bring speed, accuracy and efficiency to the iterative process of data examination. Retinal variables like color value (saturation), size and shape are good candidates to mark subjective inferences of data.

2 DYNAMIC TOOLS FOR DATA "POKING"

The hand-crafted representations shown so far are productive and generative of insight, and with training in text manipulation functions in Excel, can be generated relatively quickly. However, their production takes up valuable time in a design environment that is seeing shorter and shorter development cycles. This approach of visualizing qualitative research data also introduces a new step into the analytic process, delaying the bottom-up, thematic analysis that is the lifeblood of the project. How then might we bring greater efficiency to this meta examination of the data?

THE APP PARADIGM

The app paradigm—small, focused solutions to well-defined problems—offers an interesting model for the design of new tools that might automate the tedious process of designing data displays. The app paradigm fits the way design researchers already work: they apply a series of independent methods and tools to crack specific problems. Collectively these methods and tools provide rigor and insight to advance the project, but the tool combination is flexible and not proscribed. The app-as-focused-tool is, in fact, preferable to a comprehensive platform that is feature-packed but builds in complexity and dependencies that can slow down progress.

How might an app-like approach work here? The app mindset suggests a good solution will perform one or two key functions quickly, effectively and with little time investment. For qualitative research purposes, a series of tools that provide temporary environments to explore or "poke" the data quickly

Figure 6. This prototype data display tool reads in .csv files and builds an interactive display. Here the analyst has chosen to investigate shopping log entries by study participant. Immediately evident is the long purple bar representing Barb's entries, alerting the analyst to be careful and consider that she constitutes an unusually large number of the entries. Prototype by Ted Pollari, MDes candidate 2012.

to see what’s inside would materially inform the more advanced analysis to come.

The visualizations presented in this paper are all representations of .csv files that were exported from an online research environment. These files were cleaned up to remove unnecessary data, given new column headers that make sense to humans and then modified to combined or break apart data chunks into more optimal units of information. Once data is encased in a matrix format, with its key variables labeled and organized in a predictable fashion, applets can be designed to display that data in an interactive, dynamic environment that supports meta data explorations in ways that static Excel representations cannot.

A PROTOTYPE APP: DYNAMIC DATA EXPLORATIONS

Figure 6 demonstrates one such tool in development. It is designed to help researchers working with multi-variant data and who would benefit from insight into how the data falls out by all variables, rather than by a singly-selected variable, as is required to create the Excel visual representations.

This tool, executed in Java, allows the analyst to quickly display data by any of the variables contained in the file. Once displayed, the analyst can view the particular diary entries in a floating display brought up by a mouseover, as seen in Figure 7. This continues to supports in-context explorations and the macro/micro reading that the Excel visualizations provided, but in ways that can be changed, fine-tuned or abandoned with a dynamic, interactive response. Also in Figure 7, the analyst can select as many or as few variables to include in the floating display.

Figure 8 demonstrates a search bar that allows key word searches that highlights only entries containing those terms.

These features permit fast meta-exploration of qualitative data sets without investing much time, and can surface in minutes questions that might otherwise take days to uncover using bottom-analysis and clustering techniques. By segmenting data into user-defined families, it also facilitates faster analysis of data (“let’s group and evaluate all

Figure 7. The analyst has complete control over which of the variables are displayed in the floating display, allowing for full exploration or quick scanning of the data. Prototype by Ted Pollari, MDes candidate 2012.

Figure 8. Using the search bar at the bottom of the screen allows the analyst to keyword search all the entries. After displaying the data by segment to look for life stage shopping patterns, we see highlighted all the entries that reference Amazon as their shopping source. The scrolling text palette at the bottom offers a simultaneous display of those entries. Prototype by Ted Pollari, MDes candidate 2012.

grocery-related entries first to see why participants are not moving into online channels for perishable goods”).

HOW MANY WAYS TO VISUALIZE A MATRIX?

The tool shown here offers a conventional quantitative display format of the bar chart for its ability to present clusters of like data. What other standard visual expressions would be helpful to the design process? Visualization experts know that data can tell many stories, and the presentation format can spotlight those stories or obscure them (where only the most discerning viewer will discover them). Identifying the 3 to 6 most useful formats that fit design research and its qualitative investigations would allow the development of a suite of data “poking” applets.

3 CONCLUSION

Online research platforms are transforming design practice by giving designers unprecedented access to hard-to-reach populations and 24/7 timeframes with new efficiencies in administration. This not only opens up new areas of everyday life for

investigation, it’s changing the very nature of our user research data. The data “snippet” is emerging as a new and easily managed unit of information.

In a world of “snippets,” pattern detection and insight comes through quantity. The resulting pileup of data is hardly a unique condition, but the centrality of user research to the design profession’s process makes it particularly important to resolve. Without appropriate tools, methods and approaches for managing this data, design researchers must rely on workarounds and working memory (a limited and fragile container for important data) to negotiate the gaps in support. As Miles and Huberman (1994) note, humans are not very powerful processors of large amounts of information. Without support, Miles and Huberman explain, researchers fatigue and create provisional analytic strategies that produce predictable results:

- we gather the obvious (collect what’s easily understood)
- we reduce complex information into selective, simplified overviews

- we drastically overweigh vivid information (seeking novelty in user data is par for the course in design research).

The solution to this problem is not particularly complicated. Visual coding is a natural fit with the design research process, but designers need models and tools that show what's possible. The presentation and manipulation of qualitative data in a dynamic visual environment should also be welcomed by overwhelmed design researchers. The field of quantitative analysis provides ready guidelines for such tools—knowledge of visual perception, visual representation of data and the dynamic display of data—that can be repurposed and reinterpreted to fit the rich, messy nature of qualitative data. Examples of guidelines covered in this paper include:

- compressing big data into a single visual field that can be seen all at once;
- applying retinal variables to distinguish and cluster data in ways that can be apprehended pre-cognitively;
- creating visual displays that can be read at multiple levels simultaneously
- translating data into multiple displays to see which advances the inquiry most clearly

Visual analytic environments and the tools for visual coding, however, need adaptation to fit the evolving practices of design analysis (support for hypothesis-based manipulation and inference coding, for instance, in addition to exploring variables). These practices are already different from practices in other fields in subtle but significant ways; changes in data collection are likely to make them more so. Design requires simple solutions—at the center of this paper is how to visualize a (large) matrix—and tools that fit easily with other design research processes. The simplicity and focus of the app model provides a design-relevant set of guidelines for this.

REFERENCES

- Bertin, Jacques. (1984) *Semiology of graphics: diagrams, networks, maps*. Translated from the original 1963 text by William J. Berg. Madison, WI: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Few, Stephen (2009) *Now you see it*. Oakland, CA: Analytic Press.
- Meyer, Daniel Z and Avery, Leanne M. (2009) Excel as a qualitative data analysis tool. *Field Methods* 21:91, originally published online 20 September 2008.
- Miles, Matthew B. and Huberman, A. M. (1994) *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.